

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Study The Efficacy of Polyherbal Formulations (Vetricare Integumentary) Against DNCB Induced Atopic Dermatitis in Mice

Purva Joshi, Dr. Sushma Ghadigaonkar*, M. G. Ghadigaonkar

Department of Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology Mumbai Veterinary College, Mumbai Vetrina Healthcare Pvt Ltd, Pune.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 11 June 2025

Keywords:

Vetricare, Vetricare Integumentary, DNCB, Curcuma longa, Aloe vera, Terminalia chebula, AD, Atopic dermatitis

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15642311

ABSTRACT

Background: Atopic dermatitis (AD) presents formidable challenges in Veterinary dermatology due to its persistent nature and diverse clinical manifestations, including itching, redness, swelling, and skin lesions. Despite advancements in therapeutic interventions like topical corticosteroids and immunomodulatory agents, a significant portion of AD patients continue to struggle with persistent symptoms and frequent flare-ups. **Hypothesis:** This study aimed to explore the effectiveness of Vetricare Integumentary in alleviating AD-like symptoms. **Animals:** A total of 64 BALB/c mice (8 normal; 54 DNCB-treated) were divided into nine groups. **Material and Methods:** Group A served as the normal control, while Group B had AD-like symptoms induced through repeated application of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene (DNCB) on the ear and dorsal skin (positive control). From the 14th day onwards, Group C received standard treatment Prednisolone @ 3mg, Group D, E, F and G were administered with Vetricare Integumentary at different doses (0.1ml, 0.5ml, 1ml and 2ml). Groups F through H received varying doses of Vetricare Integumentary for two weeks to assess their anti-pruritic effects. **Results:** Results indicated that Vetricare Integumentary at different doses, alleviated DNCB-induced AD-like symptoms, demonstrated by improvements in body weight gain, reductions in skin lesions, dermatitis scores, ear thickness, and total leukocyte count values. Histopathological analysis revealed that Vetricare Integumentary at 0.1ml, 0.5ml, 1.0ml and 2ml doses reduced inflammatory cell infiltration into DNCB-induced skin lesions. Moreover, this Vetricare Integumentary also decreased the DNCB-induced elevation of Th2 cytokines interleukin (IL)-4 and Th1 cytokines IFN- γ . **Conclusions:** These findings suggest that Vetricare Integumentary holds promise as a therapeutic approach for managing atopic dermatitis.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Sushma Ghadigaonkar

Address: Department of Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology Mumbai Veterinary College, Mumbai Vetrina Healthcare Pvt Ltd, Pune.

Email ✉: sushmaghadigaonkar@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

Atopic dermatitis (AD) presents a significant challenge in veterinary dermatology due to its persistent nature and the wide variety of clinical manifestations it can produce. This inflammatory skin condition affects many animals and is marked by chronic symptoms, recurrent flare-ups, and a diverse range of issues, including itching, redness, swelling, and skin lesions. The causes of AD are complex, involving a combination of genetic factors, dysregulated immune responses, environmental triggers, and compromised skin barrier functions. Therapeutic options for atopic dermatitis include emollients, topical and systemic corticosteroids, antimicrobials, and immunomodulating agents (Leung *et al.*, 2007). Corticosteroids exert potent actions by terminating cytokine production, suppressing the expression of adhesion molecules, and inhibiting leukocyte chemotaxis. However, they are also associated with adverse effects such as abnormal metabolism, growth suppression, and increased susceptibility to infections (Hon *et al.*, 2011). Although topical steroids and oral antihistamines are commonly used to treat atopic dermatitis, their use can be accompanied by side effects. Consequently, research efforts have focused on identifying safer and more effective plant-derived compounds that can modulate the pathological mechanisms of atopic dermatitis, including antihistamine effects and inhibiting Th2 responses and IgE production (Abraham *et al.*, 2019). Despite advancements in treatment options, such as topical corticosteroids and immunomodulatory agents, many animals suffering from AD continue to experience persistent symptoms and frequent flare-ups. This ongoing struggle emphasizes the urgent need for new and effective treatment approaches that can address the intricate nature of this disorder. Vetricare Integumentary, developed by Vetrina Healthcare Pvt Ltd in Pune, India, claims to have

antiatopic activity in dogs. Consequently, this study was designed to assess the *in-vivo* efficacy of Vetricare Integumentary in managing atopic dermatitis in mice. Recently, nutraceuticals have been proposed for the treatment of various conditions (Innes, 2004; Colitti *et al.*, 2012; Henrotin *et al.*, 2005). Additionally, some herbal medicinal products have demonstrated the ability to interact with mediators of inflammation, which may make them useful in the management of osteoarthritis (Cameron *et al.*, 2009). These products can also act as antioxidants through various mechanisms. However, so far, there have been few clinical trials conducted to verify the efficacy of these herbal medicinal products. In light of this situation and the increasing acceptance of traditional herbal preparations, Vetrina Healthcare Pvt Ltd (Pune, India) developed a Poly-herbal formulation called Vetricare Integumentary. Vetricare Integumentary claims to provide supportive therapy for chronic dermatitis and atopic dermatitis. It aims to reduce trans epidermal water loss, thereby helping to maintain skin hydration. This syrup is designed to enhance skin health from within and protect against pathogens, significantly aiding the healing process. Consequently, this study evaluated the *in-vivo* efficacy of Vetricare Integumentary in managing atopic dermatitis in mice.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The experiments was carried out in the strict accordance with the guidelines set by the committee for the purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), New Delhi. The procedures used in this study were reviewed and approved by the Institutional Animal ethics committee (MVC/IAEC/02/51/2023)

Product Detail: Vetricare Integumentary is a proprietary polyherbal formulation developed by

Vetrina Healthcare Pvt Ltd., Pune. It contains Pantothenic acid, Inositol, Nicotinamide, Choline, Histidine, Zinc, Biotin, Taurine, Ascorbic acid, EPA, DHA, *Aloe Indica*, *Curcuma longa*, and *Terminalia Chebula*.

Experimental Animals

A total of 54 healthy BALB/c mice of uniform age and weight were procured for the study from NIRRH, Mumbai. The mice were kept in cages as per the specifications of CPCSEA and given standard feed (Pelleted rat feed from NCLAS, NIN, Hyderabad) and water. An acclimatization period of 2 weeks was observed before the start of the experiment. Polyherbal formulations Vetricare Integumentary (Pantothenic acid, Inositol,

Nicotinamide, Choline, Histidine, Zinc, Biotin, Taurine, Ascorbic acid, EPA, DHA, *Aloe vera*, *Curcuma Longa* and *Terminalia arjuna*) was obtained from Vetrina Healthcare Pvt Ltd Pune as a gift sample for research purposes along with a no objection certificate of the manufacturer.

Study design and Experimental details

For the experimental design, the mice were divided into Five groups, each consisting of six mice. This grouping allows for proper allocation and comparison of the studied treatments or conditions. Groups are as follows:

Experimental design:

Group	Description	Treatment	Route of Administration
A	Group A (Normal control)	1ml Normal saline	Oral
B	Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	As per protocol	Topical
C	Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	3mg/ kg body weight	Topical /Oral
D	Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	As per protocol	Topical /Oral
E	Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	1 mg/kg body weight	Topical /Oral
F	Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	0.1ml per mice per day	Topical /Oral
G	Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary 2.0ml)	0.4ml per mice per day	Topical /Oral
H	Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	1.0 ml per mice per day	Oral
I	Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	2.0 ml per mice per day	Oral

At the end of the study on the 30th day, all animals were sacrificed, and ear and skin were collected for histopathological examination, score, and Cytokine estimation. Blood was collected on day

0 and day 30, from the retro-orbital plexus using a capillary tube, following the method outlined by Sorg and Buckner (1964), preceding the animals' sacrifice. The collected blood was preserved in

K3-EDTA anticoagulant vials for subsequent hematological analysis, with processing completed within 8 hours of collection. Additionally, a thin blood smear was prepared to facilitate the differential leukocyte count.

Induction of Atopic Dermatitis by DNCB:

The 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene (DNCB) solutions, prepared by dissolving the compound in a 1:3 mixture of acetone/olive oil to achieve concentrations of 1% (w/v) and 0.5% (w/v), were administered for the induction of atopic dermatitis. The sensitization phase involved cleaning and shaving the dorsal skin using a depilatory cream. For three consecutive days, mice, except Group A, received daily administration of a 200 μ L solution containing DNCB 0.5% (3:1, v/v) on a designated 1 cm \times 1 cm area. Subsequently, on days 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, and 29, re-exposure was administered, involving the application of 20 μ L DNCB 1% (3:1, v/v) on both ears and 100 μ L DNCB 1% on the dorsal skin, excluding Group A from this re-exposure regimen (Suryawati *et al.*, 2022).

Evaluation of study parameters:

Clinical signs: All the animals were monitored thrice daily (morning, afternoon, and evening) for clinical signs, abnormal behavior, and ill health.

Body weight: The body weight of all the mice was monitored twice a week.

Ear thickness: The thickness of the skin on the right ear of all the mice was assessed three times per week utilizing a digital vernier caliper.

Evaluation of Dermatitis Score The severity of dermatitis was evaluated using the Eczema Area and Severity Index (EASI), which considers four clinical signs:

i. Redness (erythema, inflammation)

ii. Thickness (induration, papulation, swelling – acute eczema)

iii. Scratching (excoriation)

iv. Lichenification (lined skin, furrowing, nodules – chronic eczema)

The average intensity of each sign in each body region was assessed on a scale ranging from none (0), mild (1), moderate (2), to severe (3).

Hematological examination: A volume of 0.5 ml of blood was gathered in EDTA vials to conduct a complete blood count (CBC), encompassing assessments such as white blood cell (WBC) count, WBC differential, red blood cell (RBC) count, and platelet count. These analyses were performed utilizing a Hematology Auto-analyzer. Additionally, the Differential Leukocyte count was manually conducted on a blood smear using Leishman's stain, following the methodology outlined by Benjamin (2001).

Evaluation of Cytokine: IL-4 and INF- γ : Serum samples were harvested from blood samples collected at the end of the experiment and the levels of IL-4 and IFN- γ were analysed using ELISA kits following the manufacturer's instructions.

Histopathology: Skin and ear tissue samples were collected and preserved in 10% neutral buffered formalin (NBF), with subsequent processing using the routine paraffin embedding method outlined by Aziz and Zeman (2022). The resulting tissue sections, measuring 4 microns, were then stained following the standard Hematoxylin (H) and Eosin (E) protocol as recommended by Cardiff *et al.*, 1995.

Statistical analysis

The data generated during the experiment were statistically analyzed by using a One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The comparisons between the groups and between the days were tested by the Tukey test. Values are represented as mean, standard error mean and ($P < 0.05$) considered as significant. Mean values and standard error of mean were calculated and all the values were expressed as mean \pm SEM (Graph Pad Prism 5 Software, 2007).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The results of the study were presented in the table and graphically represented in graphs and tables. The mean body weight of groups B (DN CB alone), and C (Dexamethasone @3mg), was similar and lowest among all groups. There was an improvement in body weight gain in groups D (Vetricare Integumentary 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary 0.4ml), and F (Vetricare Integumentary 1.0 ml) and G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml) had the highest weight among the treatment groups on the 30th day of treatment. There was a significant difference in body weight ($P \leq 0.001$) between the treatment and control group. The Group H and I group have similar values like normal values. The mean body weight of groups B (DN CB alone), and C

(Dexamethasone @3mg), was similar and lowest among all groups. There was an improvement in body weight gain in groups D (Vetricare Integumentary 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary 0.4ml), and F (Vetricare Integumentary 1.0 ml) and G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml) had the highest weight among the treatment groups on the 30th day of treatment. There was a significant difference in body weight ($P \leq 0.001$) between the treatment and control group. The Group H and I group have similar values like normal values.

The findings of this study were consistent with those of Lee *et al.*, (2020), Kim *et al.*, (2022), and Zhang *et al.*, (2022), Although there was no significant change in body weight for the control and experimental mice initially, there was a noticeable and statistically significant ($P \leq 0.001$) decrease in body weight for mice with DN CB-induced atopic dermatitis and those treated with Dexamethasone by the end of the 30th day of the study. Zhao *et al.*, (2020) observed comparable outcomes, linking the loss of bone density to the adverse effects of dexamethasone. Furthermore, the reduced body weight gain following glucocorticoid treatment may be attributed to diminished lean mass, as previously noted by Macedo *et al.*, (2016) and Bönisch *et al.*, (2016).

Table 1. Effect of Vetricare Integumentary on body weight in DN CB-induced atopic dermatitis on different groups

Treatment Groups	Intervals of Study		
	0 Day	14 Day	30 Day
Group A (Normal control)	18.96 \pm 0.439	23.41 \pm 0.416 ^a	27.75 \pm 0.44 ^a
Group B (DN CB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	18.83 \pm 0.459	22.25 \pm 0.359 ^b	21.5 \pm 0.683 ^{de}
Group C (DN CB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	18.83 \pm 0.459	20.91 \pm 0.49 ^{bc}	21.16 \pm 0.307 ^e
Group D DN CB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	18.75 \pm 0.309	21.16 \pm 0.278 ^{bc}	23.25 \pm 0.495 ^c

Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	18.83±0.760	20.58±0.840 ^{bc}	23.08±1.01 ^{cd}
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	18.83±0.691	21±0.718 ^{bc}	23.33±0.33 ^c
Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	18.58±0.238	19.91±0.374 ^c	23.41±0.554 ^c
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	18.91±0.650	21.08±0.611 ^{bc}	25.33±0.614 ^b
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	18.33±0.166	20.83±0.380 ^{bc}	21.83±0.600 ^{cde}

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Dexamethasone, on body weight was assessed. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB and dexamethasone groups exhibited a significant decrease in body weight compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB Vetricare Integumentary showed a higher body weight gain compared to the DNCB group. Administration of Vetricare Integumentary showed a significant effect in comparison to DNCB control and Normal control group. A significant decrease in ear thickness was observed in all three groups. Presence of polyphenolic compound Curcumin in *Curcuma longa* L. and chebulic acid, gallic acid, corilagin, chebulanin, choragic acid, ellagic acid, and chebulinic acid in *Terminalia chebula* Retz. responsible for the ear's thickness due to anti-inflammatory effects. The Vetricare integumentary at different doses showed significant effect in comparison to control and DNCB groups. Significant increases in ear thickness were observed in groups B (DNCB alone) and I (Aloe vera), while comparatively lesser increments were noted in groups D (Vetricare Integumentary 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary 0.4ml), F (Vetricare Integumentary

@ 1.0ml) and G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml). The least increment in ear thickness was observed in groups C (Prednisolone 3mg), E (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml), and F (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml) compared to the normal group. There was a statistically significant difference among the groups ($P \leq 0.001$). Administration of Vetricare Integumentary at different doses showed a significant effect in comparison to DNCB control and DNCB + Prednisolone group. A significant decrease in ear thickness was observed in all four groups of Vetricare Integumentary (@ 0.1ml, 0.4ml and 1.0ml and 2.0ml). Presence of polyphenolic compound Curcumin in *Curcuma longa* L. and chebulic acid, gallic acid, corilagin, chebulanin, choragic acid, ellagic acid, and chebulinic acid in *Terminalia chebula* Retz. Similar observations were observed by Sharma *et al.*, (2019) conducted a study and found that curcumin led to considerable clinical improvements in patients with AD-like skin lesions. These improvements included a reduction in the thickness of the epidermis and the infiltration of inflammatory cells in the dermis. Inflammatory cells in AD skin affect the redox balance and worsen the condition by promoting Th2 polarization. According to Jami

et al., (2014), the fruit of *Terminalia chebula* Retz contains hydrolyzable tannins and polyphenols which can inhibit the synthesis of arachidonic metabolites resulting in anti-inflammatory and anti-analgesics effects, leading to a decrease in skin thickness. Cronin (2003) reported that *Curcuma longa* reduces swelling by inhibiting the production of inflammatory prostaglandins from arachidonic acid, as well as regulating neutrophil function.

Table No. 2: Effect of Vetricare Integumentary on ear thickness in DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis in different groups

Treatment Groups	Intervals of Study		
	14 Day (mm)	22 Day (mm)	30 Day (mm)
Group A (Normal control)	0.213±0.005	0.248 ±0.005 ^f	0.282 ±0.004 ^e
Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	0.203±0.007	0.442 ±0.005 ^a	0.577 ±0.005 ^a
Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	0.213±0.003	0.28±0.006 ^e	0.328±0.004 ^d
Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	0.205±0.004	0.32±0.01 ^{cd}	0.432±0.011 ^b
Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	0.208±0.003	0.325±0.006 ^c	0.455±0.008 ^b
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	0.203±0.006	0.317±0.012 ^{cd}	0.445±0.012 ^b
Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	0.204±0.004	0.31±0.006 ^{cd}	0.362±0.006 ^c
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	0.203±0.003	0.303±0.005 ^d	0.342±0.01 ^{cd}
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	0.2±0.004	0.393±0.007 ^b	0.56±0.008 ^a

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Prednisolone, DNCB + (Vetricare Integumentary(0.1ml), DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary (0.4), DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary (1.0ml) on ear thickness was assessed. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB group exhibited a significant increase in ear

thickness compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB + Prednisolone, DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary(0.1ml) , DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary (0.4ml), and DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary (1.0ml) groups showed a decrease in ear thickness compared to the DNCB group. The mean thickness of the dorsal skin (means ± S.E.) of animals on day 30th for groups

A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 0.595 ± 0.008 , 0.635 ± 0.014 , and 1.133 ± 0.0415 respectively 1.248 ± 0.08 , 0.62 ± 0.014 , 0.777 ± 0.01 , depicted in table 3 and Figure 3. 0.788 ± 0.018 , 0.777 ± 0.011 , 0.665 ± 0.021 ,

Table No. 3: Effect of Vetricare Integumentary on skin thickness in DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis in different groups

Treatment Group	30th Day
Group A (Normal control)	$0.595 \pm 0.008d$
Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	$1.248 \pm 0.08a$
Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	$0.62 \pm 0.014d$
Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	$0.777 \pm 0.01c$
Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	$0.788 \pm 0.018c$
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	$0.777 \pm 0.011c$
Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	$0.665 \pm 0.021d$
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	$0.635 \pm 0.014d$
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	$1.133 \pm 0.0415b$

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Prednisolone, DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml, DNCB+ Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml on dorsal skin thickness was assessed. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB group exhibited a significant increase in dorsal skin thickness compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB + Prednisolone, and DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary groups (0.1ml, 0.4ml and 1.0ml) showed a decrease in dorsal skin thickness compared to the DNCB group. The mean dermatitis score of all mice from different groups was calculated and shown in Table 4 and the pattern of change in the score is depicted in Figure 4.4. The mean were calculated, and statistical analysis for the treatment-wise

comparison was performed. On day 0, all animals in groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H and I had a mean dermatitis score of 0, which means no dermatitis symptoms were observed among them. Statistical analysis showed no significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$) between the groups. On day 7, the mean dermatitis score (mean \pm S.E.) for groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 0 , 4.83 ± 0.307 , 4.5 ± 0.223 , 4.5 ± 0.562 , 4.66 ± 0.494 , 4.67 ± 0.21 , 4.33 ± 0.494 , 4.83 ± 0.307 , and 4.83 ± 0.307 , respectively. It's worth noting that except for group A, all other groups exhibited a nearly uniform increase in dermatitis scores. These differences were found to be statistically significant ($P \leq 0.001$). On day 21, the mean dermatitis score (mean \pm S.E.) for groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 0 , 7.66 ± 0.558 , 4.5 ± 0.341 , 5.66 ± 0.210 , 5.83 ± 0.401 , 6.33 ± 0.21 , 4.83 ± 0.542 , 4.33 ± 0.494 and 7.16 ± 0.6

respectively. There was a significant increase in the mean dermatitis score of groups B and I which was found to be statistically significant ($P \leq 0.001$). On day 30, the mean dermatitis score (mean \pm S.E.) for groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 0, 11.66 ± 0.333 , 1.33 ± 0.494 , 4.5 ± 0.223 , 4.66 ± 0.614 , 4.66 ± 0.421 , 2.16 ± 0.477 , 1.5 ± 0.428 and 11 ± 0.365 respectively. There was a significant increase in the mean dermatitis score of groups B (DNCB induced group), while the scores for groups D (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml) reduced considerably, followed by groups E (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml), F (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml), and G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml). These differences were found to be statistically significant ($P \leq 0.001$). The findings of present study align with Wang et al. (2022) observations that mice with atopic dermatitis experience severe symptoms such as edema, exfoliation, erythema, scaling, and itching.

However, treating the mice with bisdemethoxycurcumin significantly improved these dermatitis symptoms and reduced itching. Scratching behavior, which is an indicator of itching, was significantly reduced in mice treated with bisdemethoxycurcumin compared to the atopic dermatitis group. Kim *et al.* (2022) also reported similar findings, demonstrating that administering *Terminalia chebula* Retz reduced dermatitis scores compared to control mice. They attributed this effect to the inhibition of NF- κ B, STAT1, and STAT3 nuclear translocation, along with a decrease in inflammatory cytokine expression at the mRNA level. Also, Suryawati *et al.* (2022) observed outcomes consistent with the present study, showing that repairing skin barrier damage with a moisturizing nanoemulgel containing turmeric rhizome extract reduced dermatitis scores.

Table No. 4: Effect of Vetricare Integumentary on dermatitis score in DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis in different groups

Treatment Groups	Intervals of Study		
	7 th Day	21 st Day	30 th Day
Group A (Normal control)	0 ^b	0 ^g	0 ^d
Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	4.83 ± 0.307^a	7.66 ± 0.558^a	11.66 ± 0.333^a
Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	4.5 ± 0.223^a	4.5 ± 0.341^{ef}	1.33 ± 0.494^c
Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	4.5 ± 0.562^a	5.66 ± 0.210^{cde}	4.5 ± 0.223^b
Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	4.66 ± 0.494^a	5.83 ± 0.401^{cd}	4.66 ± 0.614^b
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	4.67 ± 0.21^a	6.33 ± 0.21^{bc}	4.66 ± 0.421^b

Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	4.33±0.494 ^a	4.83±0.542 ^{def}	2.16±0.477 ^c
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	4.83±0.307 ^a	4.33±0.494 ^f	1.5±0.428 ^c
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	4.83±0.307 ^a	7.16±0.6 ^{ab}	11±0.365 ^a

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Prednisolone, DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary (0.1ml, 0.4ml and 1.0ml) on dermatitis score was assessed. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB group exhibited a significant increase in dermatitis score compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB + Prednisolone, and DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary groups (0.1ml, 0.4ml and 1.0ml) showed a decrease in dermatitis score compared to the DNCB group. The mean total leukocyte count (TLC) values (mean \pm S.E.) of animals on day 0 for groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 7.017 \pm 0.304, 7.033 \pm 0.328, 7.333 \pm 0.327, 7.05 \pm 0.281, 7.3 \pm 0.434, 7.35 \pm 0.308, 7.18 \pm 0.341 and 7.33 \pm 0.210 respectively as show in Table No 5. The mean TLC values of mice in all groups were similar. There was no statistically significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$). On day 30, the mean TLC values (mean \pm S.E.) of animals for groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 7.983 \pm 0.156, 21.817 \pm 1.08, 8.883 \pm 0.299, 12.983 \pm 0.33, 13.25 \pm 0.634, 13.283 \pm 0.697, 9.733 \pm 0.577,

9.3 \pm 0.447 and 21.617 \pm 1.565 respectively. The mean TLC values of groups B (DNCB alone), D (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml), F (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml), Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml were significantly higher than those of group A ($P \leq 0.001$). In contrast, the TLC values of Group C (Prednisolone 3mg), Group E (Vetricare Integumentary), and Group F (Vetricare Integumentary) were statistically like the normal group. The following study found that applying DNCB to mice led to an increase in the total white blood cell count as well as individual subtypes like neutrophils, basophils, eosinophils, monocytes, and lymphocytes. This suggests that there was an inflammatory reaction in mice following DNCB application, which is consistent with the findings of Yousif & Abu-Raghif (2020) and Hwang et al. (2021). The study also proposes that the anti-inflammatory effects of *Curcuma longa L.* and *Terminalia chebula Retz.* may be due to a decrease in total white blood cell counts, as suggested by Mujumdar et al. (2000) and Chandrasekaran et al. (2013), respectively.

Table No.5: Effect of Vetricare Integumentary on total WBC count in DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis in different groups

Treatment Group	WBC in thousands/cmm at Day 0	WBC in thousands/cmm at Day 30
-----------------	-------------------------------	--------------------------------

Group A (Normal control)	7.267±0.307	7.983±0.156
Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	7.017±0.304	21.817±0.1.08
Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	7.033±0.328	8.883±0.299
Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	7.333±0.327	12.983±0.33
Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	7.05±0.281	13.25±0.634
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	7.3±0.434	13.283±0.697
Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	7.35±0.308	9.733±0.577
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	7.18±0.341	9.3±0.447
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	7.33±0.210	9.3±1.565

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Prednisolone, DNCB+ Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml, DNCB+ Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml, DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml on TLC was assessed. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB group exhibited a significant increase in TLC value compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB+ Prednisolone, DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary groups showed a decrease in TLC value compared to the DNCB group. On day 30, the mean IL-4 concentration values (mean \pm S.E.) for groups A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, and I were 18.365 \pm 1.47, 50.175 \pm 1.60, 23.428 \pm 1.40, 34.508 \pm 2.50, 38.015 \pm 2.35, 37.235 \pm 2.15, 26.908 \pm 1.27, 26.107 \pm 1.47, and 48.782 \pm 1.24, respectively. The mean IL-4

concentration values in group B (DNCB alone) were significantly higher than those in groups D (Vetricare Integumentary@ 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml), F (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml) and G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml). However, there was no significant difference in mean IL-4 concentration values between groups C (Prednisolone), D (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml) and F (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml) and G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml). It was observed that the mean IL-4 concentration values in the DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis group were significantly higher than those in the healthy control group. Treatment groups showed a significant decrease in IL-4 values compared to DNCB induced group. Similar observations were reported by Lee *et al.*,

(2016) Sharma *et al.*, (2019), and Wang *et al.*, (2022) reported that Curcumin administration @200mg reduced serum IL-4 levels and IgE. Th2-promoting cytokines (TSLP/IL-33) and Th2 cytokines (IL-4/IL-5/IL-13/IL-31) were markedly suppressed, along with reduced STAT-6 phosphorylation and GATA-3 expression. Development of Atopic Dermatitis (AD) is caused by an imbalance in the Th1/Th2 cell ratio among patients. This results in Th2 dominance, leading to an increase in IgE and IL-4 levels. The researchers

identified IL-6 and IL-4 as primary pro-inflammatory cytokines that regulate immune cell differentiation and the production of various inflammatory mediators. These cytokines play a crucial role in the complex immunological milieu associated with AD (Bernard *et al* 2012). Curcumin interacts with several proteins, suppresses kinase activity, modulates the expression of cytokines, enzymes, and cell survival proteins, and influences the activation of transcription factors (Agrawal *et al.*, 2017).

Table No. 6: The Effect of Vetricare Integumentary on IL-4 concentration in DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis in different groups of mice

Treatment Group	IL-4 concentration at day 30 (pg/ml)
Group A (Normal control)	18.365±1.47 ^d
Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	50.175±1.60 ^a
Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	23.428±1.40 ^{cd}
Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	34.508±2.50 ^b
Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	38.015±2.35 ^b
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	37.235±2.15 ^b
Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	26.908±1.27 ^c
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	26.107±1.47 ^c
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	48.782±1.24 ^a

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Prednisolone, Vetricare Integumentary on IL-4 concentration was assessed. Data are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB group exhibited a significant increase in IL-4 concentration compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB+ Prednisolone DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml, DNCB +

Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.4ml, and DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml groups showed a decrease in IL-4 concentration compared to the DNCB group. The mean concentration of IFN- γ (mean ± S.E.) in animals on day 30 was as follows: group A - 69.75±1.52, group B - 308.483±2.53, group C - 81.757±1.95, group D - 154.25±1.88, group E - 160.167±2.11, group F - 157.4±2.38, group G - 97.405±2.06, group H - 89.047±2.41, and group I - 305.85±2.36 represented in table 7.

The mean IFN- γ levels in group B was significantly higher than in groups C, D, E, F, and G. However, the mean IFN- γ levels in groups C (Prednisolone 3mg), D (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml), E (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml), and F (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml), G (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml) were lower than in atopic dermatitis group B (DNCB), while in groups D (Vetricare Integumentary), E (Vetricare Integumentary), and F (Vetricare Integumentary), and Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml the mean concentration of IFN- γ was not significantly different ($P \geq 0.05$). The study observed a significant increase in mean IFN- γ levels in the DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis group compared to the healthy control group. Chen *et al.*, (2004) suggested that the onset of atopic dermatitis is primarily driven by Th2 cytokines. They also proposed that the disease process involves the interaction of Th2 and non-Th cytokines, as well

as various Th1 proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-12 and IFN- γ . Similar findings were reported by Kim *et al.*, (2022) with *Terminalia chebula* extract @ 100mg /kg, they found that inflammatory cytokines IFN γ , IL-8, IL-4, and IL-6 significantly decreased after treatment with *Terminalia chebula* extract. The result might be *Terminalia chebula* contains chebulagic acid and chebulinic acid which has been reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory effects by reducing the IFN γ , IL-8, IL-4, and IL-6. In the line Lee *et al.*, (2016) found that treatment with p-hydroxycinnamic acid (HCA), derived from the roots of *Curcuma longa*, led to a reduction in the intracellular levels of signature cytokines, such as IFN γ , in both Th1-polarized and Th2-polarized cells. In contrast to the present study result in Zhang *et al.*, (2009); Rubab and Ali (2016); Wang *et al.*, (2022) found an increase in IFN- γ level after DNCB treatment.

Table No. 7: The effect of Vetricare Integumentary on IFN- γ concentration in DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis in different groups of mice

Treatment Group	IFN- γ concentration at Day 30 (pg/ml)
Group A (Normal control)	69.75 \pm 1.52 ^f
Group B (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis)	308.483 \pm 2.53 ^a
Group C (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis + Prednisolone)	81.757 \pm 1.95 ^e
Group D DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.1ml)	154.25 \pm 1.88 ^b
Group E (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 0.5ml)	160.167 \pm 2.11 ^b
Group-F (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1.0ml)	305.85 \pm 2.36 ^a
Group-G (DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis+ Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2.0ml)	157.4 \pm 2.38 ^b
Group-H (Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 1ml)	97.405 \pm 2.06 ^c
Group I Polyherbal formulations (Vetricare Integumentary @ 2ml)	89.047 \pm 2.41 ^d

The impact of various treatments including Normal control, DNCB, DNCB+ Prednisolone, DNCB + *Curcuma longa* (CL), DNCB + *Terminalia chebula* (TC), DNCB + Aloe vera, Vetricare Integumentary on IFN- γ concentration was assessed. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The DNCB group exhibited a significant increase in IFN- γ concentration compared to the control ($P \leq 0.001$). Conversely, the DNCB + Prednisolone, DNCB + CL, DNCB + TC, and DNCB + Vetricare Integumentary groups showed a decrease in IFN- γ concentration compared to the DNCB group.

Histopathology

The study concluded with the sacrifice of the animals at the end of the 30th day. Following this, their ears and dorsal skin were promptly excised and fixed in 10% formalin for 24 hours. The tissues were then dehydrated using an ascending alcohol series and embedded in paraffin wax. Sections were cut to a thickness of 5 microns and stained with haematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Images were captured using a light microscope. In Group A (the normal control group), the dermal and epidermal layers displayed an unaltered architecture indicative of the absence of any pathological changes (see Plates 1 and 2). In contrast, animals in Group B (the positive control for atopic dermatitis, treated with DNCB) showed significant alterations (see Plates 3, 4, 5, and 6). These included notable epidermal thickening, conspicuous hyperkeratosis, and infiltration of inflammatory cells. Additionally, moderate instances of spongiosis, edema, congestion, and haemorrhage were evident in both the dorsal skin and ear tissues. Groups C (Prednisolone @ 3mg, see Plates 7 and 8) exhibited a resemblance of normalcy in their skin histology, although minimal signs of hyperkeratosis, thickening, and edema were observed. On the other hand, animals in

Groups D (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 9 and 10), E (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 11 and 12), and F (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 13 and 14) displayed moderate histological changes. These changes included evident hyperkeratosis, infiltration of inflammatory cells, and mild edema, affecting both the epidermis and dermis layers of the dorsal skin and ear tissues. Finally, Group G (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 15, 16 and 17) showed milder alterations, characterized by slight hyperkeratosis, cellular infiltration, and edema upon careful histopathological examination. The study concluded with the sacrifice of the animals at the end of the 30th day. Following this, their ears and dorsal skin were promptly excised and fixed in 10% formalin for 24 hours. The tissues were then dehydrated using an ascending alcohol series and embedded in paraffin wax. Sections were cut to a thickness of 5 microns and stained with haematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Images were captured using a light microscope. In Group A (the normal control group), the dermal and epidermal layers displayed an unaltered architecture indicative of the absence of any pathological changes (see Plates 1 and 2). In contrast, animals in Group B (the positive control for atopic dermatitis, treated with DNCB) showed significant alterations (see Plates 3, 4, 5, and 6). These included notable epidermal thickening, conspicuous hyperkeratosis, and infiltration of inflammatory cells. Additionally, moderate instances of spongiosis, edema, congestion, and haemorrhage were evident in both the dorsal skin and ear tissues. Groups C (Prednisolone @ 3mg, see Plates 7 and 8) exhibited a resemblance of normalcy in their skin histology, although minimal signs of hyperkeratosis, thickening, and edema were observed. On the other hand, animals in Groups D (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 9 and 10), E (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 11 and 12), and F (Vetricare Integumentary, see

Plates 13 and 14) displayed moderate histological changes. These changes included evident hyperkeratosis, infiltration of inflammatory cells, and mild edema, affecting both the epidermis and dermis layers of the dorsal skin and ear tissues. Finally, Group G (Vetricare Integumentary, see Plates 15, 16 and 17) showed milder alterations, characterized by slight hyperkeratosis, cellular infiltration, and edema upon careful histopathological examination. Similar findings were observed by Lee *et al.*, (2016), Sharma *et al.*, (2019), Wang *et al.*, (2022), and Suryawarti *et al.*, (2022) found that Curcumin had an inhibitory effect on 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene (DNCB)-induced atopic dermatitis (AD) in female BALB/c mice. They observed that compared to the control group, Curcuma longa resulted in milder epidermal hyperplasia, spongiosis, and a dermal infiltrate consisting of lymphocytes, neutrophils, and eosinophils during histopathological examination. Nam et al (2011), Sakakul et al (2013), Cui et al (2014), and Kim et al (2022) reported that significantly decreased epidermis and ear thickness, reduced inflammation by decreasing redness, compared to the positive control group (*Terminalia arjuna*), with fewer infiltrating cells was observed in histopathological analysis

CONCLUSION: The present study concluded that Vetricare Integumentary is effective against DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis. In this study, a BALB/c mouse model was used to induce atopic dermatitis through DNCB exposure. Mice in the positive control group exhibited symptoms such as decreased body weight gain, increased ear and skin thickness, elevated dermatitis scores, an increased total leukocyte count, higher cytokine levels, and histopathological changes typical of atopic dermatitis. In contrast, the treatment groups demonstrated significant improvements across all measured parameters, particularly in body weight

gain, ear and skin thickness, dermatitis scores, and total leukocyte count, following the administration of glucocorticoids and Vetricare Integumentary. Histopathological analysis further confirmed the beneficial effects of Vetricare Integumentary treatment. Moreover, treatment with Vetricare Integumentary resulted in a notable reduction in cytokine levels, specifically IL-4 and IFN- γ , highlighting its potential to alleviate the inflammation associated with atopic dermatitis.

REFERENCES

1. Abraham Fikru Mechesso, Seung-Jin Lee, Na-Hye Park, Jin-Yoon Kim, Zi-Eum Im, Joo-Won Suh and Seung-Chun Park. Mechesso. BMC Preventive effects of a novel herbal mixture on atopic dermatitis-like skin lesions in BALB/C mice. Complementary and Alternative Medicine (2019) 19:25
2. Aziz, S. J., and Zeman-Pocornich, C. E. (2022). Tissue processing. Immunohistochemistry and Immunocytochemistry: Methods and Protocols, 47-63.
3. Bönisch, C., Irmeler, M., Brachthäuser, L., Neff, F., Bamberger, M. T., Marschall, S., and Beckers, J. (2016). Dexamethasone treatment alters insulin, leptin, and adiponectin levels in male mice as observed in DIO but does not lead to alterations of metabolic phenotypes in the offspring. Mammalian Genome, 27, 17-28.
4. Benjamin, M. M. (2001). Outline of Clinical Veterinary Pathology. USA: Colorado State University.
5. Bernard, F. X., Morel, F., Camus, M., Pedretti, N., Barrault, C., Garnier, J., and Lecron, J. C. (2012). Keratinocytes under fire of proinflammatory cytokines: bona fide innate immune cells involved in the physiopathology of chronic atopic dermatitis and psoriasis. Journal of Allergy, 2012.
6. Cardiff, R. D., Miller, C. H., & Munn, R. J. (2014). Manual hematoxylin and eosin

- staining of mouse tissue sections. *Cold Spring Harbor Protocols*, 2014(6), pdb-prot073411.
7. Cronin, J. R. (2003). Curcumin: Old spice is a new medicine. *Alternative & complementary therapies*, 9(1), 34-38.
 8. Chandrasekaran, C. V., Sundarajan, K., Edwin, J. R., Gururaja, G. M., Mundkinajeddu, D., and Agarwal, A. (2013). Immune-stimulatory and anti-inflammatory activities of *Curcuma longa* extract and its polysaccharide fraction. *Pharmacognosy Research*, 5(2), 71.
 9. Chen, L., Martinez, O., Overbergh, L., Mathieu, C., Prabhakar, B. S., and Chan, L. S. (2004). Early up-regulation of Th2 cytokines and late surge of Th1 cytokines in an Atopic Dermatitis model. *Clinical & Experimental Immunology*, 138(3), 375-387
 10. Chen, L., Martinez, O., Overbergh, L., Mathieu, C., Prabhakar, B. S., and Chan, L. S. (2004). Early up-regulation of Th2 cytokines and late surge of Th1 cytokines in an Atopic Dermatitis model. *Clinical & Experimental Immunology*, 138(3), 375-387.
 11. Cameron Melainie, Joel J. Gagnier, Christine V. Little, Tessa J. Parsons, Anette Blümle, Sigrun Chrubasik (2009). Evidence of Effectiveness of Herbal Medicinal Products in the Treatment of Arthritis. *Phytotherapy research*, 23 (12): 1647-1662.
 12. Hwang, D. H., Koh, P. O., Kang, C., and Kim, E. (2021). *Rosa davurica* Pall. improves DNCB-induced Atopic Dermatitis in mice and regulates TNF- α /IFN- γ -induced skin inflammatory responses in HaCaT cells. *Phytomedicine*, 91, 153708.
 13. Kam-Lun Hon, Ting Fan Leung, Ho Chung Yau, Thomas Chan (2012) Paradoxical use of oral and topical steroids in steroid-phobic patients resorting to traditional Chinese medicines, 8: 263-267.
 14. Yves Henrotin, Christelle Sanchez, Marc Balligand.(2005): Pharmaceutical and nutraceutical management of canine osteoarthritis: Present and future perspectives. *The Veterinary Journal*, Volume 170, Issue 1, July 2005, Pages 113-123
 15. John F. Innes. (2004). Nutraceuticals for osteoarthritis: what is the evidence?, *The North American Veterinary Conference - 2004 Proceedings*:774-775.
 16. Lee, Y. S., Ryu, H. W., Yang, W. K., Park, M. H., Park, Y. C., Kim, D. Y., and Kim, S. H. (2021). A combination of *Olea europaea* leaf extract and *Spirodela polyrhiza* extract alleviates atopic dermatitis by modulating immune balance and skin barrier function in a 1-chloro-2, 4-dinitrobenzene-induced murine model. *Phytomedicine*, 82, 153407
 17. Kim, H., Kim, J. R., Kang, H., Choi, J., Yang, H., Lee, P., and Lee, K. W. (2014). 7, 8, 4'-Trihydroxyisoflavone attenuates DNCB-induced atopic dermatitis-like symptoms in NC/Nga mice. *PloS one*, 9(8), e104938.
 18. Kim, J., Park, S., Jeon, B. S., Jang, W. S., Lee, S. J., Son, Y., and Lee, S. S. (2016). Therapeutic effect of topical application of curcumin during treatment of radiation burns in a mini-pig model. *Journal of Veterinary Science*, 17(4), 435-444.
 19. Kim, S. J. (2018). The Inhibitory Effect of Gooseberry on DNCB-induced Atopic Dermatitis in vivo and in vitro. *Biomedical Science Letters*, 24(4), 349-356.
 20. Kimura, T., and Doi, K. (1999). Dorsal skin reactions of hairless dogs to topical treatment with corticosteroids. *Toxicologic Pathology*, 27(5), 528-535.
 21. Jami, M. S. I., Sultana, Z., Ali, M. E., Begum, M. M., and Haque, M. M. (2014). Evaluation of analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities on ethanolic extract of *Terminalia chebula* fruits in experimental animal models. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*, 2014.

22. Macedo, A. G., Krug, A. L. O., Souza, L. M., Martuscelli, A. M., Constantino, P. B., Zago, A. S., and Amaral, S. L. (2016). Time-course changes of catabolic proteins following muscle atrophy induced by dexamethasone. *Steroids*, 107, 30-36.
23. Sharma, S., Sethi, G. S., and Naura, A. S. (2020). Curcumin ameliorates ovalbumin-induced Atopic Dermatitis and blocks the progression of atopic march in mice. *Inflammation*, 43, 358-369.
24. Sorg, D. A., and Buckner, B. (1964). A simple method of obtaining venous blood from small laboratory animals. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 115(4), 1131-1132.
25. Suryawati, N., Wardhana, M., Bakta, I. M., and Jawi, M. (2022). Moisturizing Nanoemulgel of Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) Rhizome Extract Ameliorates Atopic Dermatitis-like Skin Lesions in Mice Model through Thymic Stromal Lymphopoietin, Interleukin-13, and Interleukin-17. *Biomolecular and Health Science Journal*, 5(2), 81-87.
26. Wang, Y., Zhang, P., Zhang, J., and Hong, T. (2022). Inhibitory Effect of Bisdemethoxycurcumin on DNCB-Induced Atopic Dermatitis in Mice. *Molecules*, 28(1), 293.
27. Zhang, E. Y., Chen, A. Y., and Zhu, B. T. (2009). Mechanism of dinitro chlorobenzene induced dermatitis in mice: role of specific antibodies in pathogenesis. *PLoS One*, 4(11), e7703
28. Zhang, R., Zhang, H., Shao, S., Shen, Y., Xiao, F., Sun, J., and Yan, M. (2022). Compound traditional Chinese medicine Dermatitis ointment ameliorates inflammatory responses and dysregulation of itch-related molecules in Atopic Dermatitis. *Chinese Medicine*, 17, 1-19.
29. Zhao, H., Jiang, X., and Chu, W. (2020). Shifts in the gut microbiota of mice in response to dexamethasone administration. *International Microbiology*, 23, 565-573.

HOW TO CITE: Purva Joshi, Dr. Sushma Ghadigaonkar*, M. G. Ghadigaonkar, Study the Efficacy of Polyherbal Formulations (Vetricare Integumentary) Against DNCB Induced Atopic Dermatitis in Mice, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 2235-2251. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15642311>

